

A PROPOSED NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE WITH ENHANCED SECURITY AND CONNECTIVITY FOR BARANGAY SAN FRANCISCO

NIVAN C. SUAREZ, MABALACAT CITY COLLEGE
PRINCES ANN F. BAUTISTA, MABALACAT CITY COLLEGE
AVIONA MARGARETH C. DIAZ, MABALACAT CITY COLLEGE
ALYANNC E VAUGHN G. LAXAMANA, MABALACAT CITY COLLEGE

ABSTRACT

Reliable network infrastructure is essential for secure communication, efficient resource sharing, and effective public service delivery in local government units. This study developed a proposed Network Infrastructure Plan (NIP) for the Barangay Hall of San Francisco, Mabalacat City, Pampanga, to address existing issues related to poor connectivity, limited wireless coverage, network congestion, inadequate security controls, and lack of network scalability. A descriptive-developmental research design was employed using the Cisco Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize (PPDIOO) lifecycle model as the framework for network planning and development. Data were gathered through interviews, site observations, and network assessments to determine the current network condition and identify operational requirements. Based on the findings, a proposed network infrastructure was designed and simulated using Cisco Packet Tracer. The proposed design incorporated a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology, Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) segmentation, Access Control Lists (ACLs), dual-ISP redundancy, structured cabling, managed switches, wireless access points, and enhanced network security mechanisms. Validation by IT experts yielded an overall weighted mean of 2.84, interpreted as Acceptable, indicating that the proposed plan is feasible, practical, and suitable for implementation. The study concluded that the proposed network infrastructure can significantly improve connectivity, strengthen data security, optimize network management, support future scalability, and enhance the efficiency of barangay operations and public service delivery.

Keywords: *Extended Star Topology, Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN), Access Control Lists (ACL), Dual-ISP Redundancy, Network Segmentation, Cisco Packet Tracer*

INTRODUCTION

The barangay is recognized as the most basic unit of government in the Philippines, serving as the primary link between citizens and the state (Republic Act No. 7160, 1991). Barangay halls perform various administrative and public service functions, including processing official documents, managing community

programs, coordinating disaster response, and maintaining peace and order. As these responsibilities continue to expand, the systems supporting barangay operations must evolve to meet the demands of modern public administration (Development Academy of the Philippines, 2022).

Technology has become a key enabler of efficient governance, with network infrastructure serving as a fundamental component of modern government operations. A well-designed network enables resource sharing, efficient communication, secure data access, and timely service delivery across departments (Forouzan, 2022). Without a reliable network infrastructure, organizations may continue to experience operational inefficiencies despite having access to computers and internet-based applications (Poojari, 2025).

This need is particularly evident in local government units where resources are often limited, yet the demand for responsive public service remains high. Many barangay halls continue to rely on basic and unstructured network configurations that are inadequate for current operational requirements. Poor connectivity, wireless dead zones, lack of logical network segmentation, and insufficient security mechanisms are among the common challenges that affect service quality and organizational efficiency (Marcelo et al., 2025; TP-Link, 2024)

These challenges were observed at the Barangay Hall of San Francisco, Mabalacat City, Pampanga. Based on interviews with barangay officials and an assessment of the existing network environment, the facility relies primarily on a single router with limited coverage and management capabilities. As a result, users experience unstable connectivity, network congestion, limited wireless coverage, and security vulnerabilities that hinder daily operations and public service delivery.

To address these concerns, this study proposed a secure, scalable, and efficient Network Infrastructure Plan for the Barangay Hall of San Francisco. The proposed design incorporates a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology, structured cabling, Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) segmentation, Access Control Lists (ACLs), enterprise wireless access points, and dual-ISP redundancy to

improve connectivity, security, reliability, and network performance. The Extended Star Topology has been widely applied in network monitoring and infrastructure systems due to its scalability and centralized management capabilities (Abdillah, 2022). The study aimed to develop and evaluate a network infrastructure plan capable of supporting the operational requirements of the barangay hall while enhancing the delivery of public services.

This study was guided by the Cisco Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize (PPDIOO) lifecycle model. The PPDIOO model is a systematic network design framework developed by Cisco that provides a structured approach for developing, managing, and optimizing network infrastructures throughout their entire lifecycle (Shabir, 2023). It emphasizes proper planning and preparation of network requirements, detailed design of network architecture, implementation of configurations, continuous operation and monitoring, and ongoing optimization to improve performance, security, and scalability. The framework provided a systematic approach for assessing the existing network environment, identifying network requirements, designing and simulating the proposed infrastructure using Cisco Packet Tracer, and evaluating its suitability through expert validation. The resulting Network Infrastructure Plan is intended to serve as a practical solution for improving connectivity, strengthening network security, and supporting future technological growth within the Barangay Hall of San Francisco.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. The framework begins with the assessment of the existing network

condition of the Barangay Hall of San Francisco to identify issues related to connectivity, coverage, security, and scalability. The identified requirements guided the application of the Cisco PPDIOO lifecycle model, which served as the framework for planning, designing, simulating, and evaluating the proposed network infrastructure. The framework ultimately produced a secure, scalable, and efficient Network Infrastructure Plan intended to enhance network performance and support the operational requirements of the barangay hall.

METHODS

The study was conducted at the Barangay Hall of San Francisco, which serves as the primary administrative and public service center of the barangay. Data were gathered through site observations, interviews with barangay officials, and an assessment of the existing network environment. The assessment focused on identifying issues related to connectivity, wireless coverage, network performance, security, resource sharing, and scalability.

Based on the collected data, network requirements were analyzed and used as the basis for developing the proposed network infrastructure. The proposed design utilized a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology incorporating an Edge Router, managed switches, enterprise-grade wireless access points, structured cabling, and dual-ISP connectivity. Network security mechanisms, including Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs), Access Control Lists (ACLs), firewall protection, Secure Shell (SSH), and port security, were integrated into the design to enhance security and traffic management.

The proposed network infrastructure was simulated using Cisco Packet Tracer. The simulation included the configuration of VLANs, Router-on-a-Stick inter-VLAN routing, Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), trunking, EtherChannel, wireless connectivity, and redundancy mechanisms. Network functionality was verified through connectivity testing, inter-VLAN communication testing, routing verification, and security validation.

RESULTS

The assessment of the existing network infrastructure at the Barangay Hall of San Francisco revealed several limitations affecting network performance and service delivery. The facility relied on a single router for internet connectivity, resulting in unstable connections, limited wireless coverage, network congestion, and inadequate security controls. Wireless dead zones were identified in the Session Hall, outdoor waiting areas, and portions of the Day Care Center. The absence of network segmentation and centralized management further increased the risk of unauthorized access and reduced overall operational efficiency.

Figure 2
Barangay San Francisco 1st Floor-Based Layout

Figure 3
Barangay San Francisco 2nd Floor-Based Layout

Figures 2 and 3 present the proposed first-floor and second-floor physical network layouts of the Barangay Hall of San Francisco. The diagrams illustrate the placement of offices, workstations, networking devices, wireless access points, and structured cabling routes throughout the facility. The proposed arrangement was designed to optimize cable management, improve network accessibility, simplify maintenance activities, and support future network expansion. Strategic placement of network devices also ensures efficient connectivity and adequate wireless coverage across all operational areas of the barangay hall.

Based on the assessment findings, a proposed Network Infrastructure Plan was developed using a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology. The design incorporated an Edge Router, managed switches, enterprise-grade wireless access points, structured

cabling, and dual-ISP connectivity. Six Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs) were implemented to logically separate administrative, operational, wireless, guest, surveillance, and management traffic. Access Control Lists (ACLs), firewall protection, Secure Shell (SSH), and port security mechanisms were also integrated to strengthen network security.

Figure 4
Logical Topology Diagram

Figure 4 illustrates the logical topology of the proposed Network Infrastructure Plan. The design follows a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology composed of edge, distribution, and access layers. The topology incorporates VLAN segmentation, dual-ISP connectivity, managed switches, wireless access points, and centralized routing functions. The logical structure enables secure communication between authorized network segments while maintaining traffic isolation for administrative, operational, guest, CCTV, and management networks. This design improves network performance, security, reliability, and scalability.

The proposed design was evaluated by Information Technology experts using a structured evaluation instrument. The evaluation assessed the network architecture, security, feasibility, performance, scalability, documentation, and overall effectiveness of the proposed infrastructure. Weighted mean analysis was used to summarize and interpret the evaluation results.

Cisco Packet Tracer simulation results demonstrated the successful implementation of VLAN segmentation, Router-on-a-Stick inter-VLAN routing, Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), trunking, EtherChannel connectivity, and wireless access deployment. Connectivity tests confirmed successful communication among authorized VLANs while maintaining isolation of restricted network segments. Access Control Lists (ACLs) effectively regulated inter-VLAN traffic, preventing unauthorized access to sensitive administrative resources. These results indicate that the proposed design successfully achieved its intended connectivity, security, and traffic management objectives.

The proposed Network Infrastructure Plan was evaluated by IT experts using a structured evaluation instrument covering network architecture, security, feasibility, compatibility, performance, governance, and validation criteria. The summarized evaluation results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Evaluation Results, Weighted Mean, and Overall Weighted Mean

Evaluation Criteria	Mean	Interpretation
Network Architecture & Design (Planned)	3.13	Acceptable
Security Architecture & Controls (Designed)	2.67	Acceptable
Compliance & Standards Alignment	2.13	Needs Improvement
Risk Management (Pre-Implementation)	2.6	Acceptable
Implementation & Technical Feasibility (Theoretical Validation)	2.93	Acceptable
Resource and Cost Planning	2.93	Acceptable
Technology and Compatibility (Planned)	3.08	Acceptable
Operational Planning (Pre-Designed)	2.92	Acceptable
Performance & Capacity Planning	3.00	Acceptable
Documentation Quality & Completeness	2.89	Acceptable
Governance & Review Readiness	3.00	Acceptable
Validation & Expert Review Criteria	2.83	Acceptable
Overall Weighted Mean	2.84	Acceptable

Table 1 presents the evaluation results of the proposed Network Infrastructure Plan based on expert validation. The overall weighted mean of 2.84, interpreted as Acceptable, indicates that the proposed design meets the technical and operational requirements of the Barangay Hall of San Francisco. Among the evaluation criteria, Network Architecture and Design received the highest rating of 3.13, reflecting the validators' confidence in the suitability of the proposed topology and network structure. Similarly, Technology and Compatibility (3.08) and Performance and Capacity Planning (3.00) received favorable evaluations, demonstrating the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed design. Although Compliance and Standards Alignment obtained the lowest mean score of 2.13, the rating still falls within the

acceptable range and highlights areas for future improvement in documentation and standards compliance. Overall, the findings suggest that the proposed Network Infrastructure Plan is feasible, reliable, and suitable for implementation within the barangay hall environment.

The simulation results and expert validation collectively demonstrate that the proposed Network Infrastructure Plan successfully achieved its intended objectives of improving connectivity, strengthening network security, enhancing resource management, and supporting future scalability. These findings provide the basis for the interpretation and analysis presented in the succeeding discussion section.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that the existing network infrastructure of the Barangay Hall of San Francisco was insufficient to support the growing operational and communication requirements of the barangay. The assessment revealed issues related to unstable connectivity, wireless dead zones, network congestion, lack of security controls, and limited scalability. These findings suggest that the existing single-router setup could no longer adequately support the increasing number of users, devices, and digital services utilized by the barangay hall.

The proposed Network Infrastructure Plan addressed these limitations through the implementation of a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology, structured cabling, managed network devices, and strategic wireless access point deployment. A star topology is a network architecture in which all devices are connected to a central device, such as a switch or router, allowing efficient data transmission, easier troubleshooting, and improved network management (Ungvarsky, 2023). In a hierarchical extended star design, multiple star networks are interconnected, enabling better scalability and structured segmentation of network traffic. The successful simulation results demonstrated that the proposed design can provide more stable connectivity, wider wireless coverage, and improved resource sharing compared to the existing network environment. The elimination of wireless dead zones and the separation of network functions across multiple layers support the principle that properly structured network architectures improve reliability and simplify network management.

The implementation of VLAN segmentation and Access Control Lists (ACLs) significantly enhanced network security by separating administrative, operational, guest, CCTV, and management traffic into distinct logical networks. This approach reduces unnecessary broadcast traffic and minimizes the risk of unauthorized access to sensitive information. These findings are consistent with previous studies reviewed in the literature, which emphasized that network segmentation and access control mechanisms are effective strategies for strengthening

organizational network security and improving traffic management.

The integration of dual-ISP redundancy and EtherChannel technology further improved the reliability of the proposed infrastructure. By providing alternative communication paths and backup internet connectivity, the design reduces the impact of service interruptions and supports continuous barangay operations during network failures. This capability is particularly important for government offices that rely on internet-based communication, record management, and public service delivery.

The expert evaluation results support the practicality and feasibility of the proposed design. The overall weighted mean of 2.84, interpreted as Acceptable, indicates that the proposed infrastructure meets the operational requirements of the barangay hall and can serve as a viable solution for improving network performance, security, and scalability. Although the Compliance and Standards Alignment criterion received a lower rating than the other categories, the overall evaluation confirms that the proposed design provides a strong foundation for future network modernization efforts.

Overall, the study demonstrates that a properly planned and structured network infrastructure can significantly improve connectivity, security, manageability, and operational efficiency within a barangay environment. The results also suggest that similar local government units experiencing comparable networking challenges may benefit from adopting structured network designs that incorporate segmentation, redundancy, and centralized management. Future studies may further validate these findings through actual implementation and performance testing in a real-world deployment environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrated that the existing network infrastructure of the Barangay Hall of San Francisco was inadequate to support its operational and public service requirements due to issues related to connectivity, wireless coverage, network security, and scalability. Through a systematic assessment and network planning process, a structured Network Infrastructure Plan was developed to address these limitations.

The proposed infrastructure, which incorporated a Hierarchical Extended Star Topology, VLAN segmentation, Access Control Lists (ACLs), dual-ISP redundancy, managed network devices, and structured cabling, provided a practical solution for improving network performance, security, and reliability. Simulation and validation results confirmed that the proposed design can support efficient communication, secure resource sharing, organized traffic management, and future network expansion.

The findings indicate that implementing a structured and segmented network architecture can significantly enhance the operational efficiency of barangay offices and strengthen their capability to deliver digital public services. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of adopting enterprise networking principles within local government units to ensure secure, reliable, and scalable network environments.

Future work may focus on the actual deployment and performance evaluation of the proposed infrastructure, as well as the integration of advanced technologies such as network automation, IPv6, centralized wireless management, and enhanced cybersecurity solutions to further improve local government network operations.

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